

Effect of minerals (macro and micro) on alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase activity during acetic acid production by an ethanol resistant strain of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀

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Abstract : To overcome the limitation of low productivity, some conditions are to be established for the control of micro organism activity, so that their multiplication and successive functioning can be favored. During the growth period, mineral supplements are necessary to enhance the activity of different enzymes. Addition of right mixture of minerals (both macro and micro), can make yeast to perform better than ever. In this study, it has been found that, 0.1% NaCl, 0.01% CaCl₂, 0.125% KH₂PO₄, 0.125% K₂HPO₄, 0.05% MgSO₄.7H₂O, 1% Na₂HPO₄.2H₂O, 1 mg/L boric acid, 10 µg/ml each of Fe²⁺, Mn²⁺ and Zn²⁺ is the optimum requirement for our organism to produce the maximum amount of acetic acid i.e. 10.678 g/L.

Keywords : Acetic acid, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, macro and micro elements.

Introduction

Microorganisms require specific minerals for growth and metabolic activities. This requirement varies with the type of organism as well as the nature of the basal medium used.

Yeast has a complex nutritional requirement¹. To overcome the limitation of low productivity of acetic acid, some conditions are to be established to favor the multiplication and successive functioning of the organisms². Each enzyme catalyzes a different reaction and also has specific nutrient requirement for optimum performance. So the studies of the optimized combinations of minerals are thus of great practical importance¹. It has been reported that Zn²⁺ is an important element for yeast cells³. At a concentration of 0.2 ppm, Zn²⁺ promotes and provides optimal growth of yeast. Considerable studies have been made in the requirement of minerals for growth of yeast. It has been reported that when phosphate was restricted, the phosphorus pool decreased before growth rate decreased and was accompanied by changes in respiration and metabolite production⁴. The threshold phosphorus concentration for yeast growth is 0.7 ppm. 0.1 g/L

MnSO₄ and 0.024 g/L FeSO₄ were detrimental to yeast growth and NaCl at 0.228 g/L limited both growth rate and the total yield of yeast cells⁵.

The present study was undertaken to examine the effect of minerals, both macro and micro, on alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase activity of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀ during the production of acetic acid.

Materials and methods :

(i) Microorganism used :

Saccharomyces cerevisiae AB₁₀₀, a newly isolated ethanol resistant strain in our laboratory have been used in these studies⁶.

(ii) Medium and cultural condition :

The maintenance media consisted of 1% D-glucose, 0.5% peptone, 0.5% yeast extract and 4% agar powder. pH was adjusted to 5.0. Organism was maintained at 30 °C for 48 h. Inoculum was harvested by washing the slant with sterile distilled water, the cell density to 2.05 × 10⁵ per ml. The medium for fermentation consisted of 10% D-glucose, 0.125% KH₂PO₄, 0.5% (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.05% MgSO₄.7H₂O. pH was adjusted to 4.5. Both me-

dium were sterilized at 121 °C and 15 lb/inch² pressure for 15 min. 250 ml conical flask containing 85 ml of the fermentation medium was inoculated with 5 ml (1.025 × 10⁶ cell/ml) of inoculum and incubated at 30 °C for 96 h. After fermentation, the cell was separated by centrifugation and the supernatant was used for the analysis of acetic acid and determination of enzyme activity.

(iii) *Estimation of acetic acid :*

Concentration of acetic acid was determined by HPLC with a TPS Spectra System apparatus using a Biorad Aminex HPX-87H column heated to 40 °C and a Refraction Index Detector (Waters 640). The mobile phase was 0.005 M sulfuric acid flowing at 0.4 ml/min^{7,8}

(iv) *Removal of impurities by chloroform extraction :*

For determination of effects of trace elements, chemicals were made free from metal impurities by chloroform extraction procedure. The components of the medium were dissolved in double distilled deionized water separately and transferred to a separating funnel. 0.1 g 8-hydroxy quinoline and 5 ml of chloroform was added and pH was adjusted to 7.2. Vigorous shaking was done for 4 min, 3 min, 2 min, and 1 min, and separating chloroform layer after each time interval. 0.1 g 8-hydroxy quinoline and 5 ml of chloroform was again added and pH was adjusted to 5.2. Similar shaking was done and finally the mixture was heated to remove all trace of chloroform. After purification, all solutions were sterilized in autoclave for 15 min at 121 °C and 15 lb/inch² pressure⁹.

(v) *Assay of alcohol dehydrogenase :*

0.1 ml of supernatant was added to the mixture of 15 mM β-NAD⁺, 50 mM sodium pyrophosphate buffer (pH 8.8) and 95% ethanol and incubated for 6 min at 25 °C in a suitably thermostatted spectrophotometer. Absorbance was recorded at 340 nm. Enzyme activity was expressed as μu/ml. One unit of enzyme activity represents the amount of enzyme which can convert 1.0 μmole of ethanol to acetaldehyde per minute at pH 8.8 at 25 °C^{7,10}.

(vi) *Assay of aldehyde dehydrogenase :*

0.1 ml of supernatant was added to the mixture of 20 mM β-NAD⁺, 1 (M) tris-HCl buffer (pH 8.0), 100 mM acetaldehyde solution, 3 (M) KCl and 1 (M) 2-mercaptoethanol and incubated for 5 min at 25 °C in a suitably thermostatted spectrophotometer. Absorbance was recorded at 340 nm. Enzyme activity was expressed as

μu/ml. One unit of enzyme activity represents the amount of enzyme which can oxidize 1.0 μmole of acetaldehyde to acetic acid per minute at pH 8.0 at 25 °C in presence of β-NAD⁺, potassium and thiols^{7,11}.

(vii) *Statistical analysis :*

Data were presented as the mean of at least three independent experiments along with SEM. Statistical analysis of data was done by Student's *t* test, by using MS Excel, and two measurements were statistically significant if the corresponding *p* value was <0.05.

Results and discussion

(i) *Effect of NaCl and CaCl₂ on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of Saccharomyces cerevisiae AB₁₀₀ :*

NaCl and CaCl₂ are required for yeast growth and flocculation. To study their effects, fermentations were carried out with different concentrations, like – 0.05%, 0.1%, 0.2% and 0.005%, 0.01%, 0.02%, respectively. Fig. 1 indicates that, 0.1% of NaCl and 0.01% of CaCl₂ produces maximum acetic acid. Higher and lower concentrations of NaCl and CaCl₂ produces lower amount of acetic acid and cell growth due to osmotic stress.

(ii) *Effect of different phosphate sources on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of Saccharomyces cerevisiae AB₁₀₀ :*

Phosphate sources are mainly required to activate the enzymes to produce the phospholipids to maintain cell membrane, which keeps the cell intact. To study the effect of different phosphate sources, fermentations were carried out using both KH₂PO₄ and K₂HPO₄ with concentrations – 0.05%, 0.075%, 0.1%, 0.125%, 0.15%. Fig. 2 shows that, 0.125% of both KH₂PO₄ and K₂HPO₄ produces maximum acetic acid and cellular growth. Higher and lower concentrations are not effective for acetic acid production and enzyme activity due to inactivation of enzymes.

(iii) *Effect of different concentrations of MgSO₄·7H₂O on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of Saccharomyces cerevisiae AB₁₀₀ :*

MgSO₄ is essential for ATP synthesis, the energy

Fig. 1. (A and B) Effect of NaCl on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀. (C and D) Effect of CaCl₂ on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀.

Fig. 2. (A and B) Effect of KH₂PO₄ on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀. (C and D) Effect of K₂HPO₄ on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀.

supplement, which keeps the cell active. Different concentrations of $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ like - 0.02%, 0.03%, 0.04%, 0.05%, 0.06%, 0.07% and 0.08% were studied and 0.05% was found as the optimal concentration (Fig. 3 (A and B)).

(iv) *Effect of Na_2HPO_4 and boric acid on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀* :

Effect of Na_2HPO_4 and boric acid were also studied with concentration, like - 0.1%, 0.2%, 0.3%, 0.4%, 0.5%, 0.75%, 1.0%, 1.25% and 0.05, 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.25 mg/L respectively. Figs. 3 (C and D) and 4 (A and B) indicate that, addition of 1.0% Na_2HPO_4 and 1.0 mg/L boric acid give the maximum production of acetic acid and enzyme activity.

yeast. They are also required as a cofactor to activate the enzymes. Effect of different trace metals have been studied, like - Fe^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mo^{6+} and V^{3+} in very minute quantities. Concentrations used in this study were in $\mu g/ml$ level, such as -1 to 20 $\mu g/ml$. Fig. 4 (C and D) to Fig. 8 show that, only Zn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} and Mn^{2+} have the positive effect at the concentration 10 $\mu g/ml$ each.

It has been found that, with the increasing concentrations, in case of Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and V^{3+} , there is very minute decrease in acid production due to slight inhibition of both the enzymes alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase.

Fig. 3. (A and B) Effect of $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀. (C and D) Effect of $Na_2HPO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀.

(v) *Effect of some trace elements on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀* :

Trace metals are highly effective for the growth of

But, it is found that, in case of Cu^{2+} and Mo^{6+} , there is a drastic fall in acid production with the increasing concentrations. It may be due to the toxic effect of Cu^{2+} and Mo^{6+} on the two main enzyme's activity.

Fig. 4. (A and B) Effect of boric acid on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀. (C and D) Effect of FeSO₄·7H₂O on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀.

Fig. 5. (A and B) Effect of MnSO₄·H₂O on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀. (C and D) Effect of ZnSO₄·7H₂O on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀.

Fig. 6. (A and B) Effect of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀. (C and D) Effect of $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀.

Fig. 7. (A and B) Effect of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀. (C and D) Effect of $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB₁₀₀.

Fig. 8. Effect of NH_4VO_2 on acetic acid production and activity of alcohol dehydrogenase and aldehyde dehydrogenase of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AB100.

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